

Superconductivity induced by external pressure in $\text{Eu}_{3-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{Bi}_2\text{S}_4\text{F}_4$ ($x=1,2$) compounds

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Abstract:

The interplay between superconductivity and Eu^{2+} magnetic ordering in BiS_2 based $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrBi}_2\text{S}_4\text{F}_4$ is studied by means of electrical transport and magnetic measurements under external hydrostatic pressure. The parent $\text{Eu}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{S}_4\text{F}_4$ (Eu-3244) which shows superconductivity at 1.5 K [1] is different from other BiS_2 superconductors in that they are intrinsic superconductors; namely, no external doping is required to induce superconductivity. The effect of Sr-doping in Eu sites, T_c gradually decreases from 1.5 K to 0.48 K (Sr=1) and there is no sign of SC can be detected further increasing Sr content at $x=2$ [2,3]. The decreased Eu^{3+} population, and the corresponding lower charge carrier density, may be the main origin for the suppression of superconductivity. We have studied the temperature-pressure phase diagram of two materials $\text{Eu}_{3-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{Bi}_2\text{S}_4\text{F}_4$ ($x = 1$ and $x = 2$) by electrical resistivity and magnetic measurements down to 2 K. Semiconducting resistive behavior observed in both the materials under ambient conditions transforms into metallic behavior as externally applied pressure gradually increases. Superconductivity is observed in both the materials at and above applied pressure $P = 2.37$ GPa. Under the highest pressure $P \sim 2.9$ GPa applied in our measurements, T_c is ~ 9.8 K in $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrBi}_2\text{S}_4\text{F}_4$ ($x = 1$) and 8.2 K in $\text{EuSr}_2\text{Bi}_2\text{S}_4\text{F}_4$ ($x = 2$). Upper critical field $H_{c2}(0) \sim 3.04$ T ($x = 1$) and 1.17 T ($x = 2$) is estimated from magnetic field dependent resistivity measurements at 2.9 GPa. Using the Arrhenius equation, we estimate the thermally activated flux flow (TAFF) activation energy U_0 as 116 K in $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrBi}_2\text{S}_4\text{F}_4$ and 39 K in $\text{EuSr}_2\text{Bi}_2\text{S}_4\text{F}_4$. At 2 K, DC magnetic susceptibility measurements indicate S-type paramagnetic behavior. Our work gives commonality of pressure effect on bismuth oxysulfide based superconductors and also it's uncovers the significance of electron carrier density in the high- T_c superconducting phase.

Reference:

1. Zhai H F et al., J. Am. Chem. Soc. 136, 15386 (2014).
2. Z. Haque et al., (Journal of Inorg chem. - (ACS)- (Accepted – Feb-2017)
3. Pan Zhang et al., Supercond. Sci. Technol. 30, 015005 (2017).